

***THE EFFECT OF NONLINEAR CONTACT UPON NATURAL FREQUENCY OF DELAMINATED STIFFENED COMPOSITE PLATE**

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SUMMARY: The effect of nonlinear contact upon natural frequency of the stiffened composite plate with predamages, such as delamination of skin panel and/or debonding interfaces between skin panel and stiffeners, is studied by the finite element method, based on hump resonance principle. A formula of element stiffness and mass matrices for the composite stiffened plates is deduce by using the first order shear deformation theory combined with the selecting numerical integral scheme, while of global damping matrix is constructed by Raleigh mode damping model in conjunction with Adam's' strain energy method. A virtual interface nonlinear contact element, called Hertz' discontinuous spring, is also employed for simulating the separate/contact mode state along the interfaces of delamination and/or debonding regions during the vibration process. The dynamic analysis method for the plates is established by a precise time integration method, and the natural frequencies are determined by the frequency/response curve. By some numerical examples, the delaminating and debonding effects upon the natural frequencies of the plates are discussed. The method and conclusions would be useful for composite structures designers.

KEYWORDS: Natural Frequency, Delaminating and debonding effects, Virtual interface nonlinear contact element, Hump resonance, Precise time integration method, Stiffened composite plate.

INTRODUCTION

Advanced stiffened composite materials are increasingly used in structural designs of aircraft, helicopters, and spacecraft due to their desirable properties such as high strength and stiffness, lightweight, fatigue resistance, and damage tolerance, etc. However, composites are very sensitive to the damage induced during their fabrication or service life. Delaminations of the skin panel and/or debonding interfaces between the skin panel and stiffeners are found to be one kind of the important pre-failure modes in the stiffened composite structures, that are often preexisting or are generated by external low velocity impact by foreign objects during the manufacturing process and/or in the service life. However the initial-delamination and/or debonding interface under dynamic load can significantly alter the dynamic properties such as natural frequency, damping ratios and response of the structures, hence a clear understanding of their dynamic characteristics is of more importance for designing and maintaining the composite structures.

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The investigation and analysis of natural frequencies for the delaminated beams/plates are of great interest to engineers and mechanics scientists and so far many valuable papers have been published. It is well known that natural frequencies and corresponding mode of the structures can be easily evaluated by some existing schemes based on an *Eigen-value* problem. However, an experimental observation finds out that, the vibration modes of the delaminated plates with a certain combination of delaminating size and shape would be varied with time, namely, there exist the contact and/or separate states in the interface of delamination and/or debonding region [1], thus the vibration problem is inherently a nonlinear one. For tackle the difficult dynamic contact problem, Mujumdar and Suryanarayana[2] have assumed that the delaminates of beam are “Constrained” to have an identical transverse displacement, which is in contrast to the “free model” of Wang et al.[3] where the sub-laminates are free to vibrate. This ‘full constrained model’ is lack of physical nature and excludes the possible opening vibration mode of sub-laminates, in addition, the “free model”, as will be pointed out in present published papers, result in interpenetration of the delaminated sub-laminates, which is an impossible mode. Recently, Nevertheless Luo and Hanagud [4], Hong and Chen [5], and Chen and Hong [6] have respectively carried out the dynamic response analysis of a delaminated beam and plate by employing a piecewise linear spring model inserted in the delaminated region. Wang and Tong [7] have established a nonlinear anti-interpenetration constrained model to study on the vibration mode of isotropic delaminated beam. Yet, it is seem that there not exist a solution strategy which well evaluates the natural frequency and corresponding mode which truly reflect the physical and mathematical characteristics of the contact/separation problem.

The present paper addresses on study of the free vibration characteristics for delaminated and/or debonded stiffened composite plates, a novel nonlinear virtual interface contact model based on Hertz contact law will be employed to reflect contact/separation states during the vibration process, and that will be combined with a lump resonance finite element method to well determine natural frequencies and corresponding vibrate modes. Numerical results indicate that the delamianton and/or debonding effects of on the variety of frequency and mode of the plates are significant.

FORMULATIONS AND MODELING OF DYNAMIC ANALYSIS BY FEM

Formulations of element stiffness and mass matrices

Displacement field based on the first order shear deformation theory

A stiffened laminated plate consists of the skin panel and stiffeners. The skin panels are simulated by plate element and the stiffeners are idealized as beams. As the first-order shear deformation theory, the displacement fields for the plate and beam element can be expressed as follows [8]:

For the plate element:

$$\begin{aligned} u &= u_0(x, y) + z\theta_y(x, y) \\ v &= v_0(x, y) - z\theta_x(x, y) \\ w &= w_0(x, y) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

For the beam element:

$$\begin{aligned}
u &= u_c(x) + z\theta_y(x) \\
v &= -z\theta_x(x) \\
w &= w_c(x)
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Where u_0, v_0, w_0 and θ_x, θ_y in Eq. (1) denote translational and rotational displacement components in the mid-plane of the plate, respectively; and u_c, w_c and θ_x in Eq. (2) are translational and rotational displacement components in the mid-plane of the beam.

Because the stiffener is attached to the upper or lower surface of the skin panel (as shown in Fig.1), according to the conditions of displacement compatibility along their line of connection, thus the nodal displacement relationship between the stiffener and the skin panel can be obtained as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u_c \\ w_c \\ \theta_x \\ \theta_y \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & e \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u^0 \\ v^0 \\ w^0 \\ \theta_x \\ \theta_y \end{Bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

Fig.1: Schematic of connection of the stiffener and the plate

where e is the distance between the mid-plane of the stiffener and that of the skin panel.

Rewrite Eq. (3) as

$$\{q^c\} = [\lambda]\{q^0\} \tag{4}$$

Where $\{q^c\}$ and $\{q^0\}$ are the nodal displacement vector for the stiffener and the skin panel, respectively.

Element stiffness and mass matrices

On basis of Hamilton's principle, the element stiffness and mass matrices for the plate and beam can be deduced in a unified form, respectively [6].

$$\mathbf{K} = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{E} \mathbf{B} d\Omega \tag{5}$$

$$\mathbf{M} = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{R} \mathbf{N} d\Omega \tag{6}$$

Where N is shape function matrix defined for each node; \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{R} denote strain-node displacement matrix, elastic matrix, and mass density matrix; respectively.

Formulations of element damping matrix

Dissipated Energy

As well be known, in dynamic analysis of the laminated composite structures, the effect of damping behavior of the composites on the dynamic response of their structures must be considered. Assuming the damping behavior of the laminated composite structures to be slight weakness, an approximate energy method provided by Adams can be employed in the dynamics analysis [9]. Hence, the dissipated energy density of the lamina can be separated into five components:

$$\begin{aligned}\delta(\Delta U) &= \delta(\Delta U_1) + \delta(\Delta U_2) + \delta(\Delta U_4) + \delta(\Delta U_5) + \delta(\Delta U_6) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}\psi_1\sigma_1\varepsilon_1 + \frac{1}{2}\psi_2\sigma_2\varepsilon_2 + \frac{1}{2}\psi_4\sigma_4\varepsilon_4 + \frac{1}{2}\psi_5\sigma_5\varepsilon_5 + \frac{1}{2}\psi_6\sigma_6\varepsilon_6\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

where ψ_i is defined the SDC component. For laminated plate with k layers, the total energy dissipation ΔU can be expressed by:

$$\Delta U = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \int_{Z_{k-1}}^{Z_k} \{\delta\}^T [\psi^k] [\bar{Q}^k] \{\delta\} dz d\Omega \quad (8)$$

where $[\psi^k]$ and $[\bar{Q}^k]$ are the stiffness and loss factor matrix for the k -th layer. The expression of loss factor matrix in the principal material coordinate system can be given by:

$$[\psi] = \begin{bmatrix} \psi_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \psi_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \psi_4 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \psi_5 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \psi_6 \end{bmatrix}$$

Modal Damping

In the current research, the preferred method of treating material damping is by determining the specific damping capacity. The specific damping capacity is defined as the energy absorbed per cycle ΔU over the strain energy U at the maximum displacement state:

$$\eta = \frac{\Delta U}{U} \quad (9)$$

Therefore, if ξ_i is defined as the modal damping ratio for the i th mode, the following equation can be written:

$$\eta_i = 4\pi\xi_i \quad (10)$$

Damping Matrix

The proportional damping model, called as Raleigh damping, is often used to dynamic analysis of engineering structure, which damping matrix is proportional to mass and stiffness matrices, the expression can be written as:

$$C = \alpha M + \beta K \quad (11)$$

where M and K are the mass and the stiffness matrix, and the factors α and β can be determined by regression method based on mode analysis.

Displacement Continuity in front of Damage

The delamination of the skin panel and interface debonding between the skin panel and stiffener are two kinds of commonly observed damage modes, which often occur in the stiffened laminated plates after low energy impact. Those damages can result in a substantial loss of dynamic stiffness and load carrying capacity of the structures.

Consider a stiffened laminated plate containing an embedded elliptic delamination as shown in Fig.2. The plate can be divided into three regions, namely two separate sublaminates located at above and below the delamination skin panel in the delaminated region, and an integral skin panel connected with above and below sub-laminates in delamination region along its outer contour. The above three regions are denoted by the subscript 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

Fig.2: Schematic of stiffened plate with a delamination

The continuity of the displacements and rotations along the delamination front must be strictly satisfied, hence the constraint equations imposed can be written as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} w &= w_1 = w_2 = w_3 \\ \theta_x &= \theta_{x1} = \theta_{x2} = \theta_{x3} & \theta_y &= \theta_{y1} = \theta_{y2} = \theta_{y3} \\ u_1 &= u_3 + \theta_y (H - h_u)/2 & u_2 &= u_3 - \theta_y h_u/2 \\ v_1 &= v_3 - \theta_x (H - h_u)/2 & v_2 &= u_3 + \theta_x h_u/2 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (12)$$

Where H and h_u denote the thickness of the base-plate and the upper sub-plate, respectively.

In the same way, the constraint equations for continuity of the displacements and rotations along the debonding interface between the skin panel and stiffener can be given, but omitted here.

Nonlinear virtual interface contact model

For a certain combination of delaminating and/or debonding size and shape, a closure would occur total and/or over parts of the delamination and/or debonding region. Unless some constraints are imposed, the two separate parts located at above and below the delaminating and/or debonding interfaces of will appear in penetration for special period during dynamic analysis process, which is an infeasible vibration mode, and the numerical error will be introduced in the results. On basis of Hertz contact law, a virtual interface piecewise nonlinear spring model is inserted along the surface of two separate parts. The relation between contact force and relative displacement is:

$$F = k_h (w_1 - w_2) (|w_1 - w_2|)^{3/2} \quad (13)$$

In which, the subscripts 1 and 2 are contact pair corresponding to upper and lower separate parts, respectively, and k_h is a specified stiffness factor given by experiment value when in the separate case and /or *zero* when in contact case.

DYNAMIC ANALYSIS METHOD BY FEM

Motion equation and precious integral scheme

According Hamilton's principle, the motion equation can be written in terms of relation:

$$\mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{C} \dot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{K} \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{P}(t) \quad (14)$$

where \mathbf{M} 、 \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{C} are the total mass matrix, stiffness and the damping matrix, while \mathbf{u} and $\mathbf{P}(t)$ are the total displacement and the force vector of the structure. It should be mentioned here, the Eq.14 is a of nonlinear dynamic-contact equation because of considering the effect of contact/separate modes during dynamic analysis process.

For avoiding solution disturbance, which often appears in Newmark and/or Wilson- θ methods hence, a precise time-integration algorithm is employed. The fundamental formulation for the algorithm is briefly introduced here.

Transforming Eq.14 into the following precise time-integration iteration formulation [10]:

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}} = \mathbf{H} \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{r} \quad (15)$$

In which

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{I} \\ \mathbf{B} & \mathbf{G} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{v} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u} \\ \dot{\mathbf{u}} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{r} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{p}(t) \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{B} = -\mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{K} \quad \mathbf{G} = -\mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{C}$$

If only consider time independent system, H is a matrix with all constant element, therefore, the general solution of above equation can be written as

$$\mathbf{v} = \exp(\mathbf{H} \bullet t) \bullet \mathbf{v}_0$$

$$t_0 = 0, \quad t_1 = \tau, \quad \dots \quad t_k = k\tau$$

Then at the time integration points:

$$v_1 = Tv_0, \quad v_2 = Tv_1, \quad \dots \quad v_{k+1} = Tv_k$$

It is clear that the key for the accurate computation of the solution V_k is to determine a precious matrix T . Once T is calculated, the solution can be repeated matrix-vector multiplications.

Presumption force varied simple harmonic curve in each integration step $t \in [t_k, t_{k+1}]$:

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}_1 \sin(\omega t) + \mathbf{r}_2 \cos(\omega t) \quad (16)$$

Then the precise time-integration method's HPD-S(Sinusoidal) formulation can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{v}(t_{k+1}) = \mathbf{T}(\tau) [\mathbf{v}(t_k) - \mathbf{a} \sin(\omega t_k) - \mathbf{b} \cos(\omega t_k)] + \mathbf{a} \sin(\omega t_{k+1}) + \mathbf{b} \cos(\omega t_{k+1}) \quad (17)$$

In which,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \mathbf{a} &= (\omega \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{H}^2 / \omega)^{-1} (\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{H} \mathbf{r}_1 / \omega) \\ \mathbf{b} &= (\omega \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{H}^2 / \omega)^{-1} (-\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{H} \mathbf{r}_2 / \omega) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (18)$$

If considering damage and separate-contact effects, H matrix should be changed in the each integration time step.

Strategy for natural frequency analysis

The natural frequencies and corresponding mode analysis of the structures is usually transformed into an eigen-value and corresponding eigen-vectors problem. The vibration modes of damaged composite plates depend on the contact/sepalate states in the interface of delaminating and/or debonding region for different vibration periods, thus it could not be employed existing computational schemes to calculate the natural frequencies of the plates.

As an experimental measurement for detecting natural frequency of the structure, a hump resonance method is proposed to solve the problem. Fig.3 illustrates a frequency/response spectrum curve for a $[0]_{16}$ laminates with a through-width delamination obtained by dynamic response analysis method, in which the coordinates λ and α are magnification parameter and non-dimensional frequency, respectively. The values of α located at peaks of the curve are of the natural frequency of the plate. The present numerical results have good agreement with that given by test [11].

(a) The first order resonance peak

(b) The second to fourth order resonance peaks

Fig3: Frequency/response spectrum curve of $[0]_{16}$ laminates with a through-width delamination

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

Perfect stiffened laminated plate

A perfect stiffened laminated square plate is considered, the dimensions for the laminate plate and stiffener $L = 300\text{mm}$; $H = 5\text{mm}$, $t_s = 10\text{mm}$. (see Fig.2). The stacking sequence of the stiffened laminates plate is $[0/90/90/0]_{2S}$ and 0_{40} respectively. The boundary condition along four edges is simply supported. The mechanical properties of for the plate and stiffener are the same, that is, $E_1 = 135.0\text{GPa}$, $E_2 = 8.80\text{GPa}$, $G_{12} = G_{23} = G_{13} = 4.47\text{Gpa}$, $\nu_{12} = 0.33$, $\rho = 1380\text{Kg /m}^3$, $\psi_1 = 0.43\%$, $\psi_2 = 3.86\%$, $\psi_4 = \psi_5 = \psi_6 = 5.72\%$ [12]. For elucidating the stiffened effect on the frequency of the plate, the values of the first eight order natural frequencies for a bare perfect plate and the stiffened plates with 3 different distances between neighboring stiffener, namely, $d = 100\text{mm}$, 150mm , and 200mm are shown in Table 1, respectively.

Table.1: Natural frequencies of $[0/90/90/0]_{2S}$ for perfect bare and stiffened laminates (Hz)

Modes	Bare	d =100mm	d =150mm	d =200mm
1	1095.6	1920.9	1701.5	1467.2
2	2714.8	3036.6	3071.3	2998.5
3	2788.2	4831.1	4142.2	3521.0
4	3834.5	5270.7	5172.3	4963.9
5	5150.8	5355.0	5251.4	5273.4
6	5230.3	6259.6	6272.0	5836.9
7	5895.0	7238.9	7034.1	6351.8
8	5976.6	7556.2	7305.5	7003.0

The results in Table 1 indicate that the values of natural frequency of the plate are effectively increased by stiffeners, and the smaller distance d , the effector. Thus, the dynamic rigidity can be improved by optimizing the distance of neighboring stiffeners.

Stiffened laminated plate with a delamination located at base-plate

For study the effect of delamination on the natural frequencies, assume a stiffened laminated square plate with an embedded circle skin delamination, which is located at the center of the plate as shown in Fig.2. The distances between neighboring stiffener $d = 100\text{mm}$ and the radius of the delamination is 30mm , while the other dimensions and properties as same as that in first example.

For sake of comparison, the values of the first eight order natural frequencies for the perfect and delaminated plates with same dimensions are listed in Table 2, respectively. From the listed results, it can be seen that the values of frequency for the delaminated plate are less than

that for perfect one, thus the reduction of dynamic rigidity caused by skin delamination should be considered for dynamic analysis of stiffened delaminated plates.

Table 2: Natural frequencies of $[0/90/90/0]_{2S}$ for the perfect and delaminated stiffened plates (Hz)

Modes	Perfect	Delaminated
1	1920.9	1864.3
2	3036.6	3040.3
3	4831.1	4722.5
4	5270.7	5024.4
5	5355.0	5267.1
6	6259.6	5987.8
7	7238.9	7001.2
8	7556.2	7277.5

Stiffened laminated plate with debonding interface between stiffener and skin panel

Fig.4 depicts a stiffened laminate plate as shown in Fig.4. The distance between neighboring stiffeners is 100mm, while the other dimensions and boundary condition of the plate, and ply-sequence and mechanical properties for the skin panel and stiffener are the same as that in the first example. Consider two kinds of debonding interface forms: (a) single debonding interface and (b) double debonding interfaces, which are located at middle of the stiffener span. The length of debonding interface $l = 60\text{mm}$. Table 3 shows the results of natural frequencies for the first 8 modes of the debonding and perfect plates, respectively. Compared the results for 3 cases demonstrates that interface debonding reduces the values of frequency, namely, dynamic rigidity, significantly. However, the extent of weakening effect is related to the vibration mode, as well as the number, length and location of the debonding interface.

Fig.4. Stiffened laminated plate with debonding interface between stiffener and base-plate

Table.3 Natural frequency of stiffened laminate with debonding between stiffener and laminate (Hz)

Modes	Perfect	(a) Single debonding	(b) Double debondings
1	1920.9	1527.7	1483.4
2	3036.6	2963.0	2953.1
3	4831.1	4259.1	3614.8
4	5270.7	5084.9	5039.5
5	5355.0	5247.7	5223.5
6	6259.6	6101.9	5961.4
7	7238.9	6438.2	6399.7
8	7556.2	7289.3	6859.7

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) The dynamic rigidity of the laminated plates can be increased by stiffener, efficiently. However its reduction can be caused by existing pre-delaminations and pre-debonding interfaces dramatically.
- (2) Compare two damaged stiffened laminated plates, in which the size of delamination and debonding interface is the same, the reduction of dynamic rigidity induced by debonding

interface between stiffener and skin panel, general speaking, is more severe than that by the delamination, however the extent of reduction depends on the vibration modes as well as the delaminating and debonding locations.

- (3) The natural frequency of the delaminated and/or debonded stiffened laminated plates is significantly influenced by mode change, which is resulted from the variety of contact and separate state along the interface of delaminating and/or debonding region during the vibration process.
- (4)The methodology, model and numerical analysis method proposed in the paper allow predicting the natural frequencies and corresponding modes of the delaminated and/or debonded stiffened plates.

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